

A MODERN TOOL FOR IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL-GRAPHIC COMPETENCE OF YOUNG TEACHERS IN THE DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The use of digital technologies is one of the main directions in the teaching of abstract professional sciences, especially today in the training of specialists. To this end, we want to introduce a new innovative platform (PTS) Professional Testing system.*

Keywords: “web-master”, “web-leader”, “web-project manager”, “web-designer”, “web-programmer”, “specialist in website promotion”.

Since independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan, great attention has been paid to the field of education. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized: “Today, when the world is changing rapidly, new challenges and threats to stability and sustainable development of nations arise, more than ever before, attention to education, spiritual, moral principles, inculcation of young people with a desire for knowledge, needs for self-improvement. Enlightenment and education are the key to the prosperity of peoples. It is enlightenment and education that lead people to good deeds, goodness, tolerance”.

One of the features of the modern development of education is its digital technologies. Digital technologies is a global social progress, the peculiarity of which is that the dominant type of activity is the collection, accumulation, production, processing, storage, transmission and use of information, carried out on the basis of modern microprocessor and computer technology, as well as on the basis of various means of information sharing.

The processes taking place in connection with the digital technologies of society contribute not only to the acceleration of the scientific and technical process, the intellectualization of all types of human activity, but also to the creation of a qualitatively new information environment of society, which ensures the development of the individual’s creative potential.

Training in computer graphics - one of the most important areas of using a personal computer, is considered today as the most important component of education. Achievements in the field of ICT update the issues of training a specialist in the field of presenting information in the form of graphic images: drawings, diagrams, drawings, sketches, presentations, animated videos, virtual worlds, etc. The professional training of future specialists in the field of computer graphics should be focused on the training of a competitive specialist in demand in the labor market in the context of the growing pace of computerization of education. From the moment of studying computer graphics in educational institutions, teachers have accumulated some experience in teaching, but the didactic system of teaching this section has not yet been formed, due to the dynamism of the field of computer graphics and the high demands of the labor market for graduates. Modern computer graphics is a fairly broad area of scientific knowledge, covering the methods, technologies and tools for creating computer two-dimensional and three-dimensional

images of various nature, as well as interactive and animated products. New consumers of computer graphics are constantly appearing; new qualified personnel are required — artists and developers of computer models and representations. In connection with the development of information technology, it is in the field of computer graphics that the newest specialties have appeared. A few years ago, for example, the new profession "web-master" was identified in the labor market, which is quite popular and highly paid today. Currently, several new related specialties have developed from the specialty "web-master", "web-leader", "web-project manager", "web-designer", "web-programmer", "specialist in website promotion", "Internet advertising specialist", "website tester" that is, more specific specializations that are taught in professional colleges become relevant. Of course, all this should be reflected in the content of the discipline.

Thus, the relevance of the research topic was revealed: to improve the methodology of teaching graphics in professional colleges, and in particular, when learning how to use the new platform of (PTS) Professional Testing system .

The aim of this article is to develop an improved methodology for teaching graphics in the environment for students of professional colleges using didactic technologies.

Object of article: the process of teaching students in professional colleges computer and engineering graphics.

The main goal of the article: methodology of teaching students in professional colleges computer and engineering graphics in the environment using didactic materials.

To achieve the intended goal it was necessary to solve the following tasks:

1. To analyze the scientific and educational literature on the topic of research,
2. To analyze the state of the organization and methods of conducting classes on the subject of "Computer and Engineering Graphics" in professional colleges.
3. Develop electronic didactic materials and, based on their application, organize classes to study the capabilities of the active program.
4. To carry out an experimental verification of the effectiveness of the proposed methodology for teaching computer graphics in the internet environment in professional colleges.

In order to solve this problem I want to recommend new platform which gives opportunities using digital and communication technologies. By our group is created new (PTS) Professional Testing system site which can teach, and testes automatically. The (PTS) gained intern the amount of information about graphics which give learns find easily any information in wanted form, which means the information in the platform is given in Audio, video, and text forms.

And now I will explain why information in the (PTS) is given forms like above.

The reason is the people is divided into three groups when they receiving information visualist, audiolist, kinesthetic .It means that visualist accept main information by watching, for audiolist important listening information but kinesthetic people understand when they do it themselves and the platform of (PTS) based on this at end of the final examples learner can take an exam in order to take certificate and to see their knowledge so from my point of view it is very useful for all of them.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the materials of this study can be successfully used in the pedagogical practice of a professional college, which will contribute to the activation of educational and cognitive activities of students.

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